

1 **State- and time-resolved observation of ultrafast intermolecular**
2 **proton transfer in hydrated biomolecules**

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I. ABSTRACT

16 Proton transfer (PT) is pivotal in numerous chemical and biochemical processes, including
17 acid-base neutralization, fast proton diffusion, DNA lesions, mutations, and the formation of
18 reactive intermediates. Recent advancements in ultrafast laser technology have enabled the
19 direct tracing of even the swiftest proton transfer processes in real-time. Here, we investigate
20 the PT dynamics of the pyrrole-water dimer initiated by electron collision, resulting in
21 the local double ionization of the pyrrole unit. The $C_4H_5N^{2+}$ dication transfers a proton
22 to a neighboring water molecule, forming deprotonated $C_4H_4N^+$ and hydronium cations
23 H_3O^+ , with both cations and one outgoing electron being measured in coincidence. The PT
24 dynamics induced by electron collision was compared with the analogical process initiated
25 by strong-field ionization. The reaction was then monitored in real-time using a femtosecond
26 pump-probe scheme in conjunction with the Coulomb explosion imaging technique. The PT
27 occurs within 39 ± 18 fs, establishing it as one of the fastest acid-base reactions observed to
28 date. The full molecular picture into the PT process are provided through nonadiabatic *ab*
29 *initio* molecular dynamics calculations. This study offers a novel perspective on radiation-
30 induced proton transfer in biomolecules.

INTRODUCTION

31 Proton transfer (PT) in the ground electronic state is a pivotal process in various do-
32 mains of chemistry and biology [1–4], and its dynamics have been under investigation since
33 the early days of fast chemical kinetics [5]. These initial observations indicated that PT
34 often occurs at an exceedingly rapid rate. In his Nobel Prize lectures, Manfred Eigen refer-
35 enced Eucken’s textbook on chemical kinetics, stating that “The rate of true neutralization
36 reactions has proved to be immeasurably fast” [5]. Utilizing relaxation techniques, Eigen el-
37 elegantly demonstrated that the PT process frequently operates as a diffusion-limited process,
38 exhibiting measurable rates on a microsecond timescale [6].

39 The advent of laser technology theoretically enabled the direct tracking of PT dynam-
40 ics. Water upon valence ionization emerged as a natural candidate for investigating PT
41 dynamics. The PT times, as determined from *ab initio* calculations conducted at various
42 levels of sophistication, consistently indicated a PT time less than 100 fs [7–11]. However,
43 femtosecond pump-probe technology, offering a time resolution of hundreds or thousands of
44 femtoseconds, only suggested that PT in liquid water occurs well below 100 fs [11]. It was
45 only recently, with the broader availability of X-ray free-electron lasers, direct spectroscopy
46 observation of PT in liquid water [12] and in a water dimer [8] became possible. Both studies
47 confirmed a lifetime of approximately 50-60 fs. Additionally, an ultrafast electron diffraction
48 study hinted at $\text{H}_3\text{O}^+\dots\text{OH}$ formation within 140 fs [13]. Notably, this conclusion does not
49 contradict previous timescales, as the ultrafast electron diffraction technique solely detects
50 the position of the heavy atoms, that relax only after the completion of the PT. Even faster
51 PT reactions in water following inner valence ionization [14] or core level ionization [15] can
52 be indirectly inferred using the core-hole internal clock.

53 The comprehensive understanding of PT in water stands in stark contrast to the limited
54 exploration of PT following the ionization of hydrated biomolecules. The significance of these
55 processes lies in their potential role in radiation damage and DNA mutations, necessitating
56 a thorough understanding of the underlying mechanisms at the molecular level [16–19]. In
57 this context, excited-state PT in biomolecular clusters has been investigated [20, 21].

58 Upon ionization, water or solute molecular cations can transfer a proton to a neighboring
59 molecule, resulting in the formation of a protonated ion and a deprotonated group. However,
60 the reaction pathways of PT between ionized water and solute molecules, or between ionized

61 biomolecules and water, remain poorly understood. The directionality of these processes is
62 particularly unclear. In a natural aqueous environment, protons can be transferred from
63 ionized water molecules to solute molecules along a water chain through the Grotthuss-type
64 mechanism [22], thereby lowering the pH value in the vicinity of the solute molecules and
65 modulating biological or chemical reactions. The transmission of protons along a water
66 chain occurs exceedingly rapidly. As mentioned above, the elementary PT process takes
67 place within 50 fs, and the nascent radical-ion pair is fully formed within 140 fs in liquid
68 water [8, 12, 13]. Ionization-induced PT between nucleobases can also be impeded by the
69 hydrogen-bonded network of the DNA-water environment; instead, protonated nucleobases
70 are generated through PT from an ionized water molecule [23]. Conversely, ionized solute
71 molecules can transfer protons to water molecules, initiating proton pumps for processes such
72 as energy and signal transduction. In the two different directions of PT processes induced by
73 outer-valence ionization, PT from water to solute, such as biomolecules, is barrierless when
74 accessing an ionized state localized in water [23]. However, when the charge is localized on
75 the biomolecule, PT from the biomolecule to the water molecule encounters a large barrier,
76 obstructing the PT pathway in this direction [23]. These findings have piqued our interest:
77 is PT unidirectional in ionized hydrated biomolecules? Is there a means to open up the PT
78 pathway from biomolecules to water molecules, and what will be the timescale?

79 An attractive approach for investigating PT dynamics is the double ionization of
80 biomolecules [24]. These states can be readily accessed through high-energy ionizing
81 radiation via Auger processes, which, however, leave the system in a mixture of states.
82 Alternatively, direct double ionization is possible either via photons or electron collision.
83 Doubly ionized biomolecules may also be produced within radiolysis, as a large number of
84 secondary electrons with a mean energy of roughly 60 eV are generated during radiolysis
85 processes [25, 26]. This serves as an important ionization source in the medium, also pro-
86 ducing molecular dications. When two charges are localized on one molecule, the system's
87 energy is generally higher than that of a state with dispersed charges due to the former's
88 higher Coulomb potential. This could facilitate a barrierless PT pathway from biomolecules
89 to water molecules. However, localized double ionization of a molecule also introduces a new
90 challenge: doubly ionized molecules are typically unstable and may undergo dissociation.
91 Consequently, PT must precede dissociation, necessitating a faster PT. Despite numerous
92 efforts, elucidating the PT mechanism from ionized biomolecules to water molecules remains

93 elusive.

94 In this study, we generated hydrated pyrrole dicationic states ($C_4H_5N^{2+}-H_2O$) with two charges
95 localized on the pyrrole unit through electron-impact (see Fig. 1(a)). The choice of the
96 hydrated pyrrole dimer as our experimental model for biological proton-relay systems stems
97 from pyrrole’s well-established reputation as a biologically active scaffold with diverse ac-
98 tivities [27, 28]. The electron-density donating position of water in the vicinity of pyrrole
99 leads to an energy reduction of the localized double ionization state ($C_4H_5N^{2+}-H_2O$), which
100 lies below the nonlocalized double ionization state ($C_4H_5N^+-H_2O^+$) [29]. Consequently, the
101 system tends to favor the locally doubly ionized state during the ionization process. We
102 anticipate a facile PT from the doubly ionized biomolecule to a water molecule, supported
103 by the experimentally observed high-yield PT channel. Further dynamical insights into PT
104 in hydrated pyrrole dicationic states are revealed through adiabatic and non-adiabatic *ab initio*
105 molecular dynamics (AIMD) simulations.

106 In our investigation, we employ two complementary approaches to unravel the PT dy-
107 namics. We trace the dynamics indirectly by scrutinizing the energetics of the outgoing
108 fragments measured in coincidence, a method applicable to cluster systems. Alternatively,
109 we directly probe the dynamics through pump-probe-type experiments. The combination
110 of electron-impact and photon-driven processes yields additional insights into the nature of
111 the formed dicationic state.

RESULTS

112 Let us start with a brief discussion of the structure and electronic configuration of the
113 pyrrole-water complex. In the pyrrole-water dimer, the pyrrole molecule forms a hydrogen
114 bond with the water molecule, characterized by a N–O distance of 3.02 Å as evaluated at
115 the CCSD/aug-cc-pVDZ level of theory. The first ionization potential is measured at 8.21
116 eV, with the electron being ionized from the highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO)
117 corresponding to the π orbital of the pyrrole unit [30]. Intriguingly, the three lowest doubly
118 ionized states of the water-pyrrole system exhibit an excess charge localized on the pyrrole
119 unit (23.26 eV (T_0), 23.41 eV (S_1), and 23.90 eV (S_2) above the ground state minimum),
120 see Table I and the Supplementary Tables S4 and S5. The localized dicationic states are
121 somewhat stabilized by the hydration [29]. The S_3 , T_1 , and higher excited states of the

122 doubly ionized cluster feature a charge delocalization between the pyrrole and water units.

Ionized MOs	State	DIP [eV]	Rel. DIP [eV]	Character
HOMO (π) + HOMO-1 (π)	T ₀	23.26	0.00	localized on pyrrole
HOMO (π) + HOMO (π)	S ₁	23.41	0.15	localized on pyrrole
HOMO (π) + HOMO-1 (π)	S ₂	23.90	0.64	localized on pyrrole
HOMO (π) + HOMO-4 (σ on water)	S ₃	24.52	1.26	delocalized
HOMO (π) + HOMO-4 (σ on water)	T ₁	24.52	1.26	delocalized

TABLE I. Double-ionization potentials (DIP), relative DIP of pyrrole-water cluster and molecular orbitals mostly involved in ionization for both singlet and triplet manifold. EOM-DIP-CCSD/aug-cc-PVDZ method was used. The relative DIP is shifted with respect to the double-ionized triplet ground state. If not stated otherwise, molecular orbitals (MOs) are localized on pyrrole.

123 In our experiments, as shown in Fig. 1(a), the localized dicationic state of the pyrrole-
 124 water complex can be populated via electron-impact ionization, followed by ultrafast PT
 125 from C₄H₅N²⁺ to H₂O molecule (see Fig. 1(b)). The fragment ions resulting from the dou-
 126 ble ionization of C₄H₅N-H₂O dimers are detected in coincidence with a COLTRIMS reaction
 127 microscope [31, 32] (see the Methods section). By measuring the time-of-flight (TOF) and
 128 position of cations hitting on the time- and position-sensitive detector, six momentum pa-
 129 rameters (three for each fragment ion) are determined for a single explosion event. The
 130 direct dissociation C₄H₅N⁺+H₂O⁺ and proton transfer C₄H₄N⁺+H₃O⁺ channels are clearly
 131 defined by the TOF correlation map between two fragments ions, which is shown in Fig. 1(c).
 132 The x and y coordinates correspond to the TOFs of the first and second ions of the coinci-
 133 dence pairs. In this map, the two-body fragmentation channel displays a diagonal structure
 134 with a slope of -1, due to the back-to-back emission of two fragments with equal momen-
 135 tum magnitude. The PT channel C₄H₄N⁺+H₃O⁺ is located to the lower right of the direct
 136 dissociation channel C₄H₅N⁺+H₂O⁺, which is attributed to the fact that the TOF of ion is
 137 positively correlated to its momentum and mass-to-charge ratio. The PT channel exhibits
 138 a significantly higher yield, approximately 2.5 times that of the direct dissociation channel,
 139 which is mainly because the PT originates from the electronic ground state of the dicationic
 140 dimer, i.e. the charge localized C₄H₅N²⁺-H₂O state.

141 In the current electron collision experiment, the PT channel can be accessed by local

FIG. 1. Schematic of COLTRIMS reaction microscope upon electron-impact and proton transfer pathway of $H_3O^+ + C_4H_4N^+$ and measured TOF correlation spectrum. (a) The local double ionization of H_2O - C_4H_5N dimer upon electron-impact; (b) Proton transfer from doubly ionized $C_4H_5N^{2+}$ to H_2O molecule; (c) Measured TOF correlation map between the first and the second cation. The cyan and green arrows represent the direct dissociation $H_2O^+ + C_4H_5N^+$ and the proton transfer $H_3O^+ + C_4H_4N^+$ channels, respectively. The vertical and horizontal lines are from false coincidence. The count intensity is color-coded on a linear scale.

142 double ionization of the hydrated pyrrole dimers, which can be determined by the measured
 143 projectile energy loss spectrum associated with the ion pair ($C_4H_4N^+ + H_3O^+$). Here, the
 144 projectile energy loss is defined as the energy difference between the incident electron (E_0)
 145 and the scattered electron (E_1), i.e., $E_{loss} = E_0 - E_1$. The energy loss spectrum is calibrated
 146 by the single ionization of helium ($E_{loss}[He^+] = 24.6$ eV). As shown in Fig. 2(a), the onset of
 147 the E_{loss} associated with the PT channel is determined as about 23.5 eV, which is in line with
 148 the double-ionization threshold of the hydrated pyrrole dimer and corresponds to the state

149 of two charges localized on the pyrrole unit (see Table I). This $C_4H_5N^{2+}-H_2O$ precursors
 150 can be formed by direct double ionization or Auger autoionization in the electron collision
 151 processes. The electron-density donating position of water reduces the double ionization
 152 threshold of pyrrole, allowing Auger decay of the lowest $C\ 2s^{-1}$ state, which is forbidden in
 153 isolated pyrrole molecules. The higher-lying $O\ 2s^{-1}$ states of water molecule can also decay to
 154 the $C_4H_5N^{2+}-H_2O$ states by electron transfer mediated decay (ETMD) [33]. In the ETMD,
 155 the pyrrole transfers an electron to the $O\ 2s$ vacancy, and the released energy results in the
 156 ionization of another electron in pyrrole. However, due to the large intermolecular distance
 157 between pyrrole and water, the overlap of the inner-valence orbital with the outer-valence
 158 orbital on the same site is much better than with the outer-valence orbital on the neighboring
 159 center [33–35]. As a result, the $O\ 2s^{-1}$ states tend to decay through the intermolecular
 160 Coulombic decay (ICD) [36] process over ETMD forming $C_4H_5N^++H_2O^+$ ions pairs, and
 161 the contribution of the ETMD channel to the localized double ionization states is arguably
 162 small. This is also confirmed by the measured E_{loss} of the PT channel, which is much smaller
 163 than the ionization threshold of $O\ 2s^{-1}$ band.

164 In the static fs laser experiment, two electrons can be removed sequentially via strong field
 165 tunneling ionization, and the probability of such sequential double ionization exponentially
 166 relies on the ionization potential for each ionization step [37]. Thus the population of
 167 the ground state of the dication (i.e., localized double ionization of pyrrole) is dominant
 168 and the same PT channel is initiated as in the electron-impact experiment. The measured
 169 kinetic energy release (KER) spectra of the PT channels in both electron-impact and fs laser
 170 experiments are presented in Figs. 2(b) and (c), which show a single peak structure at about
 171 2.6 eV. With the same initial electronic state and structure, the measured KER spectra for
 172 the PT channel match perfectly in both experiments. The KER of the Coulomb explosion
 173 channel sensitively depends on the initial intermolecular distance, and the intermolecular
 174 potential drops with $1/R$ assuming two point-like charges separated by the distance R . We
 175 may deduce the Coulomb energy by considering that the two charges are located at the
 176 center-of-mass (COM) of the molecules. For the lowest-energy configuration of hydrated
 177 pyrrole dimer, the intermolecular COM distance is about 4.12 Å [38]. This would result in a
 178 total KER of around 3.49 eV. This value lies about 0.9 eV higher than the measured KER of
 179 the PT channel, indicating that there are significant rearrangements in the structure of the
 180 complex during the PT process, and there is also a conversion of some Coulomb potential

FIG. 2. (a) Projectile energy loss spectrum for the proton transfer channel $\text{H}_3\text{O}^+ + \text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{N}^+$. The vertical dashed line represents the double-ionization threshold of the hydrated pyrrole dimer. Measured and calculated KER for the proton transfer channel $\text{H}_3\text{O}^+ + \text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{N}^+$. The solid (b) and hollow dots (c), as well as solid (d) and hollow (e) bars, represent the results of electron collision and laser experiments and AIMD and CASPT2 theoretical calculations, respectively. Error bars represent statistical s.d., and were calculated by the square root of the true coincidence counts.

181 into vibrational and rotational energy of fragments [39, 40]. In addition, the polarization
 182 forces between water and pyrrole can also contribute to the non-Coulombic effect [8, 41].

183 To quantify the timescale of PT, we designed a femtosecond pump-probe experiment
 184 wherein a linearly polarized laser functioned as the pump pulse and a temporally delayed
 185 elliptically polarized laser served as the probe pulse. As shown in Fig. 3(a), the pump
 186 pulse initiates PT by inducing local double ionization in the hydrated pyrrole dimer. The
 187 pump pulse ionizes two electrons sequentially via strong field tunneling ionization. Since the
 188 tunneling ionization exponentially relies on the ionization potential, the sequential ejection
 189 of two electrons from the pyrrole unit dominates and thus leads to the population of the
 190 double ionization ground state of hydrated pyrrole, which is supported by the fact that the
 191 measured KERs are identical in both laser and electron-impact experiments (Figs. 2(b,c)).
 192 The probe pulse acts as a disruptive pulse, converting the intermediate $\text{C}_4\text{H}_5\text{N}^{2+}\text{-H}_2\text{O}$ to
 193 $\text{C}_4\text{H}_5\text{N}^+\text{-H}_2\text{O}^+$ through single-photon absorption.

194 As illustrated in Fig. 3(a), following the localized double ionization of hydrated pyrrole

FIG. 3. (a) Schematic of the femtosecond laser pump-probe experiment and (b) yield of $\text{H}_2\text{O}^+ + \text{C}_4\text{H}_5\text{N}^+$ as a function of pump-probe time delay. In this region, we fit the yield with a decay function (red solid line) and extract the PT time $\tau = 39 \pm 18$ fs. Error bars represent statistical s.d., and were calculated by the square root of the true coincidence counts. The potential energy curves of $\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{C}_4\text{H}_5\text{N}^{2+}$ (blue solid curve), $\text{H}_2\text{O}^+ + \text{C}_4\text{H}_5\text{N}^+$ (red solid curve), and $\text{H}_3\text{O}^+ + \text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{N}^+$ (purple dashed line) are calculated using constrained DFT with Configurational Interaction approach and the B3LYP/aug-cc-PVTZ method.

195 dimers, the $\text{C}_4\text{H}_5\text{N}^{2+}$ dication and H_2O molecule approach each other due to the attractive
 196 potential between them. Since the energy gap of the local and nonlocal doubly ionized
 197 states can match the photon energy of 800 nm laser pulse, the evolving wavepacket on
 198 $\text{C}_4\text{H}_5\text{N}^{2+}\text{-H}_2\text{O}$ state prepared by the pump pulse can be projected to the $\text{C}_4\text{H}_5\text{N}^+\text{-H}_2\text{O}^+$
 199 state via single-photon absorption from the probe pulse, and then the $\text{C}_4\text{H}_5\text{N}^+\text{-H}_2\text{O}^+$ dimer
 200 dissociates rapidly to $\text{C}_4\text{H}_5\text{N}^+ + \text{H}_2\text{O}^+$ via Coulomb explosion. As the delay time increases,
 201 the wavepacket on the PES of the $\text{C}_4\text{H}_5\text{N}^{2+}\text{-H}_2\text{O}$ intermediate state culminates in PT, such
 202 that the system can no longer be excited to the $\text{H}_2\text{O}^+\text{-C}_4\text{H}_5\text{N}^+$ state in the probe pulse.
 203 As a result, the yield of the direct dissociation channel decays as increasing the time delay,
 204 which reflects the time scale of PT. Fig. 3(b) shows the time-resolved ion yields of the direct
 205 dissociation channel ranging from -100 to 400 fs. The positive time delay indicates the pump
 206 pulse arriving earlier than the probe pulse. The yield curve of the direct dissociation channel
 207 can be well fitted with a mono-exponential function:

$$Y(t) = [(Ae^{-\frac{t}{\tau}} + c) \cdot H(t)] * G(t) \quad (1)$$

208 where A represents the amplitude, τ is decay time, c is the offset, and $H(t)$ is the Heaviside
 209 step function. Through the fit, we extracted the decay time $\tau = 39 \pm 18$ fs.

210 Next, to further reveal the dynamical details of PT, we performed molecular dynamics
 211 simulations using two different approaches: we use either Born-Oppenheimer dynamics with
 212 density functional theory and quasiclassical initial conditions or non-adiabatic simulations
 213 based on correlated multi-reference potential energy surface with initial conditions sampled
 214 by molecular dynamics. We show that these two very distinct approaches provide us with
 215 very similar results, demonstrating the robustness of the PT process.

216 In the first approach, the optimized hydrated pyrrole dimer was sampled at a finite
 217 temperature (30 K in our supersonic gas jets) and stripped two outermost electrons from
 218 pyrrole (see Methods). The KER of every trajectory is obtained by summing the kinetic
 219 energies of the simulated molecular cations at $t = 500$ fs and the remaining Coulomb potential
 220 energy considering the center-of-mass (COM) distance. The calculated KER is presented
 221 in Fig. 2(d), which matches very well with the experimental results. As in previous studies
 222 on PT dynamics in water clusters [13], intermolecular PT is not a simple one-dimensional
 223 motion of a hydrogen nucleus along a hydrogen bond. Here, our AIMD calculations indicate
 224 that it also involves significant rearrangement of the other heavy atoms. As illustrated in
 225 Fig. 4, the distance between N and O atoms r_{O-N} (Figs. 4(b) and (e)), as well as H connecting
 226 to N and O atoms r_{O-H} (Figs. 4(c) and (f)) are plotted as a function of propagating time.
 227 Upon ionization, the intermolecular distance r_{O-N} undergoes a rapid decrease within 50 fs
 228 due to the increasing attractive interactions upon removing two electrons from the closed-
 229 shell pyrrole, transitioning from approximately 3.02 Å to 2.44 Å. After a brief pause in
 230 the intermediate state (N-H \cdot · O), the C₄H₄N⁺ and H₃O⁺ ions rapidly separate due to
 231 Coulomb repulsion, leading to a fast increase in r_{O-N} after 75 fs. Simultaneously with the
 232 contraction of r_{O-N} , the proton initially attached to the N atom transfers to a neighboring
 233 water molecule. At $t \sim 50$ fs, the initial N-H \cdot · O hydrogen bond breaks, and the proton
 234 transfers to a water molecule, which responds well to the experimental result of 39 ± 18
 235 fs. Subsequently, the C₄H₄N⁺ and H₃O⁺ rapidly move apart under the influence of strong
 236 Coulomb repulsion between two cations. These results indicate that despite the nearly

FIG. 4. (a) The rigid two-dimensional potential energy surface scan in triplet ground state, calculated with the CCSD/aug-cc-pVDZ method. A black curve with arrows describes the minimum-energy path toward proton transfer and subsequent Coulomb explosion. (b) + (c) Evolution of interatomic distances analyzed from AIMD simulation in triplet ground state using the B3LYP/cc-pVDZ method. Distances between O and N atoms (r_{ON}) (b) and distances between O atom and H atom on pyrrole molecule (r_{OH}) (c) as functions of time. (d) Reaction channel evolution for surface hopping starting from state T_0 with the localized charge on pyrrole molecule. The channel analysis focused on the dissociation of water molecules, or PT followed by dissociation. Other channels, such as dissociation of the hydrogen atom, were not observed. (e) + (f) Evolution of interatomic distances analyzed from the surface hopping simulation in triplet ground state. Distances between O and N atoms (r_{ON}) (e) and distances between O atom and H atom on pyrrole molecule (r_{OH}) (f) as functions of time.

237 linear hydrogen bonding between pyrrole and water molecules ($\angle N-H \cdots O \sim 178^\circ$) and
 238 the short distance between the proton-accepting and proton-donating atoms (3.02 \AA), the
 239 PT reaction coordinate is not a simple proton motion along the hydrogen bond, but also
 240 involves the motion of the heavy atoms. The initial contraction of intermolecular distance
 241 between $C_4H_5N^{2+}$ and H_2O could be an important prerequisite for intermolecular PT, which

242 is also adhered to the pattern of hydrogen-to-covalent bond conversion [42]. The revealed
243 PT process in doubly ionized biomolecules and water molecules occurs even faster than in
244 pure water clusters, potentially due to the stronger induced dipole moments between the
245 doubly ionized cations and water molecules.

246 The system is likely prepared in the ground electronic state of the dication, especially
247 within the strong-field ionization process. The Born-Oppenheimer molecular dynamics sim-
248 ulations might thus seem adequate, especially considering the good match with the experi-
249 ment. The molecular dynamics simulations in the ground adiabatic electronic state neglect
250 the possible interaction between the electronic states. As discussed above, the delocalized
251 state of the dication is positioned only 1 eV above the electronic ground state with localized
252 charge and this energy distance can even shrink within the dynamics. Furthermore, the first
253 excited state of the dication with a charge localized state is only 0.5 eV above the ground
254 state. The non-adiabatic processes potentially play a role. We have, therefore, extended
255 the non-adiabatic simulations and modeled the PT process with molecular dynamics em-
256 ploying the non-adiabatic surface hopping molecular dynamics, utilizing the multi-reference
257 wavefunction.

258 The details of the simulations are described in the Methods section. We considered five
259 different initial states, T_0 and T_4 with two charges localized on the pyrrole unit and T_1 ,
260 T_2 , and T_3 states with delocalized charges (see Table I and Supplementary Table S5 and
261 Fig. S1). The electronic structure was described with the CASPT2 electronic structure
262 method, including thus both dynamical and static correlation. The active space comprised
263 of 6 electrons in 6 MOs. Due to the computational demands, we made a larger number of
264 calculations only for the T_0 and S_1 (localized charge) states. As shown in Fig. 4(d) and
265 Supplementary Fig. S2, the PT dominated for simulations starting with a charge localized
266 on pyrrole, the total yield for the PT channel amounted to around 98%. The reaction
267 channel yields were considered at the end of the evaluation, which was set to 200 fs. The
268 non-adiabatic simulations also provided very similar distributions of the KER spectra (see
269 Fig. 2(f) and Supplementary Fig. S3) and we also equally confirm the geometrical changes
270 during the simulations (Figs. 4(e,f)).

271 In hydrated biomolecular clusters, PT from outer-valence ionized biomolecule to water
272 molecule is normally inhibited due to the high barrier along the PT path [20, 21]. The
273 reverse PT observed in the doubly ionized hydrated biomolecules implies a transformation

274 in the potential energy landscape between reactants and products. As can be seen from
275 the structure of the $C_4H_5N-H_2O$ complex (shown Fig. 1(a)) - pyrrole and water molecules
276 form a linear $N-H \cdots O$ hydrogen bond with $\angle NHO \sim 178^\circ$ and relatively short (3.02 Å)
277 distance between the proton-accepting (O) and proton-donating (N) atoms as evaluated at
278 the CCSD/aug-cc-pVDZ level of theory. However, as shown by the molecular dynamics
279 simulations described above the proton transfer coordinate is not a simple smooth proton
280 movement from nitrogen to oxygen and turns out to involve the motion of both molecules.
281 This statement can be further illustrated by the two-dimensional potential energy surface
282 (PES) scan performed for the ground state of the hydrated pyrrole dication (see Fig. 4(a) and
283 Supplementary Fig. S4), where the potential energy of the complex is plotted as the function
284 of the N-O and O-H distances. The black arrows represent the preferred proton transfer
285 path from $C_4H_5N^{2+}-H_2O$ to $C_4H_4N^+-H_3O^+$ system which is barrierless. It is clearly seen
286 that in the course of the continuous shortening of the O-H bond due to the proton migration,
287 the N-O distance also decreases, while after the formation of a delocalized dicationic system
288 $C_4H_4N^+-H_3O^+$, the N-O distance continuously increases, corresponding to the Coulombic
289 decay of the positively charged fragments $C_4H_4N^+$ and H_3O^+ . This picture is consistent
290 with our molecular dynamics simulations and implies that after the double ionization of the
291 hydrated pyrrole, the $C_4H_5N^{2+}$ dication can rapidly transfer a proton to the neighboring
292 water molecule along this pathway. It has been shown that in the pyrrole-water system,
293 the water acts as an electron-density donor to the pyrrole molecule, this effect reduces the
294 electronic density of water and makes it more costly to remove an electron from it. On
295 the other hand, the electronic density of the pyrrole is increased which lowers the energy
296 required to ionize an additional electron. As a result, the doubly ionized ground state of
297 hydrated pyrrole is assigned to the localized dicationic state, with two charges located on
298 the pyrrole molecule [29]. The preferential occupation of localized dication states due to
299 reduced double ionization energy, along with the absence of the PT barrier contribute to
300 the higher yield of the PT channel compared to the direct dissociation channel ($C_4H_5N^+ +$
301 H_2O^+) as observed in our experiments.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

302 We experimentally demonstrated an ultrafast PT in the doubly ionized hydrated biomolec-
303 ular complexes. The complete picture of the structural and dynamical properties of PT in
304 hydrated pyrrole dimer is revealed by the simultaneous investigation of the PT by electron-
305 impact double ionization, femtosecond pump-probe experiments following the strong field
306 ionization, and *ab initio* calculations. The electron-impact experiments reveal the initial
307 states and dynamical information directly, by inspecting the kinetic energy distributions
308 of the outgoing fragments and electrons. The strong field experiment allowed for a direct
309 tracing of the PT dynamics in real-time and the *ab initio* calculations have unified these
310 approaches.

311 The overall picture of the process is as follows. The PT is initiated by a localized double
312 ionization with two charges residing on the pyrrole unit. The kinetic energy distributions
313 agree well between the electron-impact and strong-field ionization experiments, indicating
314 that in both cases the lowest dicationic state is predominantly formed in both experiments.
315 In the electron-impact experiment, the energy loss spectrum is measured in coincidence
316 with the fragment ions to resolve the initial ionization state. The simulated KERs are
317 in very close agreement with these experiments both for Born-Oppenheimer molecular dy-
318 namics (assuming adiabatic dynamics on a single surface) and the non-adiabatic dynamics
319 with Landau-Zener surface hopping method, even though a non-negligible fraction of the
320 wavepacket undergoes a transition between adiabatic states. Molecular dynamics reveal an
321 intrinsic PT time below 50 fs.

322 The PT in hydrated pyrrole dimers involves a complicated collective motion rather than
323 just the one-dimensional movement of the proton along hydrogen bonds. During this process,
324 a contraction of the intermolecular distance between $C_4H_5N^{2+}$ and H_2O is observed. This
325 is supported by the two-dimensional PES scan, which indicates that the PT is barrierless
326 but not a direct process. The indirect character of the PT is typically for the process in
327 the electronic ground state [7] or low-lying ionized state while the PT following the inner
328 valence or core ionization are direct processes [14, 15]. The character of the PT for a doubly
329 ionized system is, therefore, far from evident.

330 The charge localization on the pyrrole unit is brought about by the solvent effect due
331 to the electron-donor role of water in hydrated pyrrole dimers. The localization of the two

332 charges forms the $C_4H_5N^{2+}$ - H_2O structure which corresponds to the ground state of the
333 dication, and thus leads to a higher yield of the PT channel than the direct dissociation
334 channel. The latter process is found to originate from the electronically excited state of the
335 dicationic dimer (see Table I). Utilizing the fs laser pump-probe technology, we measure a
336 PT time of (39 ± 18) fs. This demonstrates the ultrafast character of PT between doubly
337 ionized biomolecules and water molecules. The measured data are in agreement with the
338 theory, supporting again the mechanistic picture outlined above.

339 Given the significance of radiation-induced damage caused by X-rays, neutrons, and swift
340 ions, the present results are expected to shed light on the role of the water environment in
341 radiation damage of biological tissues. In both H-bonded and π -stacked nucleobase dimer,
342 solvation shuts down PT between the bases induced by single ionization [23]. Exposed to
343 these radiation sources, dications can readily be formed through direct double ionization or
344 Auger-type autoionization. It is also noted that both processes are energetically accessible by
345 secondary electrons (mean energy ~ 60 eV) which are created in large numbers by all kinds of
346 ionizing radiations [25, 26]. The PT channel from doubly ionized nucleobases to surrounding
347 water molecules is opened, which could contribute to the tautomerization of DNA base pairs
348 causing point mutations and inappropriate pairing between bases [17–19]. The ultrafast PT
349 needs to be considered in investigations and models on high-energy radiation damage in a
350 realistic environment.

351 The suppression effect of water on radiation damage to biomolecules in aqueous envi-
352 ronments has been discussed intensely in past studies [43–47]. The irradiated biomolecules
353 may avoid dissociation by energy dissipation mechanisms, such as ICD [36, 48], wherein
354 highly excited state molecules, before fragmentation, decay through filling the inner-valence
355 vacancy with an outer-valence electron, and released energy leads to the ionization of neigh-
356 boring water molecule. The currently observed PT similarly offers a way for highly excited
357 biomolecules to be shielded from ring-opening dissociation following localized decay by trans-
358 ferring a proton to neighboring water molecules. On the other hand, even the transfer of a
359 single proton from nucleic acid bases into the aqueous environment may potentially lead to
360 subsequent DNA replication errors and mutations [17–19].

METHODS

361 **Multi-particle coincidence momentum spectroscopy.** The experiment was per-
362 formed using a COLTRIMS reaction microscope spectrometer [31, 32]. The details of the
363 experimental setup have been introduced elsewhere [49, 50], and here we provide only a brief
364 overview. The hydrated pyrrole dimers are generated by helium carrier gas passing through
365 sample vapors containing water and pyrrole, respectively, followed by supersonic expansion.
366 The molecular dimers collide orthogonally with a focused electron beam, and the resultant
367 electrons and ions are guided by electric and magnetic fields to time- and position-sensitive
368 detectors. The electron beam is generated using a photoemission electron source, in which a
369 tantalum photocathode is irradiated by a pulsed 266-nm ultraviolet laser. A low electric field
370 (1.5 V cm^{-1}) is utilized to extract electrons to ensure electron momentum resolution, after
371 500 ns when the outgoing electrons have reached the detector, the electric field is raised to 25
372 V cm^{-1} to guarantee the complete spatial collection of the fragment ions. The unscattered
373 electron beam is collected by the central hole of the electron detector without generating a
374 signal. During off-line analysis, the three-dimensional momentum vector of each detected
375 particle is reconstructed from the measured TOF and position.

376 The time-resolved pump-probe technique in combination with Coulomb explosion imaging
377 is employed to track the PT dynamics. A linearly polarized laser pulse with a central
378 wavelength of 800 nm and a pulse width of 35 fs was split into two beams. One beam
379 served as the pump pulse, which ionized hydrated pyrrole dimers to the ground state of
380 dication and prepared a wavepacket, and the other beam served as the probe pulse, which
381 further projected the wavepacket to the excited state of the dication through single-photon
382 absorption process. Linearly and elliptical polarized laser pulses are used for pump and
383 probe, respectively, and their peak intensities are estimated to be 120 TW cm^{-2} and 170
384 TW cm^{-2} . A translation stage was used to control the time delay between the pump and
385 probe pulses. The COLTRIMS setup is employed to detect all the ion fragments and provide
386 their three-dimensional momenta and yields.

387 **Molecular dynamics simulations.** The Born-Oppenheimer *ab-initio* molecular dy-
388 namics simulations were performed using the Gaussian 16 package [51]. The initial condi-
389 tions, i.e. geometries of hydrated pyrrole dimers were sampled by the quasi-classical fixed
390 normal-mode sampling method under the temperature of the supersonic gas jet (30 K). The

391 populations of the initial vibrational states of the complexes were determined by Boltzmann
392 distributions. The molecular dynamics simulations were performed under the extended La-
393 grangian molecular dynamics scheme, adopting the so-called atom-centered density matrix
394 propagation (ADMP) method [52–54] using the density-functional theory (DFT) method at
395 B3LYP/cc-pVDZ level. All atoms were characterized by their three-dimensional momentum
396 vectors. Propagation was performed for a total simulation duration of 500 fs with a time step
397 of 0.5 fs. The total KER can be calculated by adding the kinetic energies of the simulated
398 two molecular cations together with the remaining Coulomb potential energy considering
399 the center-of-mass distance at this instant [39, 40].

400 **Nonadiabatic molecular dynamics simulations.** Nonadiabatic dynamics calcula-
401 tions were performed with the surface hopping scheme in its fewest switches version [55].
402 The equations of motion were integrated with the velocity Verlet integrator with a timestep
403 of 4 a.u., with a total simulation duration of 500 fs in the ABIN package[56]. The elec-
404 tronic structure was described with the extended multi-state complete active space second-
405 order perturbation theory (XMS-CASPT2). We used the cc-PVDZ basis set. The energies,
406 gradients, and non-adiabatic couplings were computed in the BAGEL electronic structure
407 package, version 1.2.0 [57]. The active space was set to 6 electrons in 6 MOs and in total
408 5 electronic states were included. The initial conditions for the surface hopping simulations
409 were generated with the molecular dynamics in a neutral state using Path Integral MD
410 combined with the quantum thermostat based on the generalized Langevin equation [58–60]
411 (PI+GLE). The temperature was set to 300 K. As the PI+GLE approach does not provide
412 physically relevant velocities, these were sampled using Boltzmann distribution probabili-
413 ties. The ω B97x functional with 6-31++g** basis set was used for the sampling simulations
414 together with the D3 dispersion correction. The electronic structure was described using
415 the TERACHEM [61] package and the ABIN package was used to integrate the equation
416 of motion with the time step of 20 a.u. and the total length of simulations equal to 29 ps.
417 KER was calculated as a sum of kinetic energies, using the COM momenta of individual
418 fragments, and Coulombic energy using the Mulliken charges on individual atoms.

419 **Potential energy calculations.** The rigid two-dimensional scan of the PES shown
420 in Fig. 4(a) was calculated using the CCSD/aug-cc-pVDZ method with the computational
421 package QCHEM version 6.1[62]. As the initial structure, we used a geometry optimized
422 using the B3LYP/aug-cc-PVTZ method in a doubly-ionized triplet ground state with the

423 distance constraint for N-O distance being 3.02 Å. Particular geometries were created by
424 changing the N-O and N-H distances with time step 0.05 Å. The $\text{H}_2\text{O}^+ + \text{C}_4\text{H}_5\text{N}^+$, H_3O^+
425 $+ \text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{N}^+$ and $\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{C}_4\text{H}_5\text{N}^{2+}$ curves in the one-dimensional PES scan shown in Fig. 3(a)
426 were calculated using constrained DFT with Configurational Interaction (CDFT-CI) ap-
427 proach and the B3LYP/aug-cc-pVTZ method. In addition, we also calculated the two-
428 dimensional PES for the proton transfer channel using the relaxed PES scan method, which
429 is presented in Supplementary Fig. S4. The scan is performed by fixing the intermolec-
430 ular N-O and O-H distances at each point, all other coordinates were optimized at the
431 CCSD/cc-pVDZ level at each step, the step size is 0.1 Å. More details can be found in the
432 Supplementary information file.

DATA AVAILABILITY

433 The data generated in this study are provided in the Source Data file. The data support-
434 ing this study are also available from the corresponding author upon request.

REFERENCES

- 435 [1] Mohammed, O. F., Pines, D., Dreyer, J., Pines, E. & Nibbering, E. T. J. Sequential proton
436 transfer through water bridges in acid-base reactions. *Science* **310**, 83–86 (2005). URL
437 <https://www.science.org/doi/abs/10.1126/science.1117756>.
- 438 [2] Nocera, D. G. Proton-coupled electron transfer: The engine of energy conversion and storage.
439 *Journal of the American Chemical Society* **144**, 1069–1081 (2022). URL [https://doi.org/](https://doi.org/10.1021/jacs.1c10444)
440 [10.1021/jacs.1c10444](https://doi.org/10.1021/jacs.1c10444).
- 441 [3] Hvasanov, D., Peterson, J. R. & Thordarson, P. Self-assembled light-driven photosynthetic-
442 respiratory electron transport chain hybrid proton pump. *Chem. Sci.* **4**, 3833–3838 (2013).
443 URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1039/C3SC51780B>.
- 444 [4] Wikström, M., Sharma, V., Kaila, V. R. I., Hosler, J. P. & Hummer, G. New perspectives
445 on proton pumping in cellular respiration. *Chemical Reviews* **115**, 2196–2221 (2015). URL
446 <https://doi.org/10.1021/cr500448t>.
- 447 [5] *Nobel Lectures* (Elsevier Publishing Company, Amsterdam, 1972), chemistry edn. URL [https:](https://www.nobelprize.org/uploads/2018/06/eigen-lecture.pdf)
448 [//www.nobelprize.org/uploads/2018/06/eigen-lecture.pdf](https://www.nobelprize.org/uploads/2018/06/eigen-lecture.pdf).

- 449 [6] Eigen, M. Protonenübertragung, säure-base-katalyse und enzymatische hydrolyse. teil i: Ele-
450 mentarvorgänge. *Angewandte Chemie* **75**, 489–508 (1963). URL [https://doi.org/10.1002/](https://doi.org/10.1002/ange.19630751202)
451 [ange.19630751202](https://doi.org/10.1002/ange.19630751202).
- 452 [7] Svoboda, O., Hollas, D., Ončák, M. & Slavíček, P. Reaction selectivity in an ionized water
453 dimer: nonadiabatic ab initio dynamics simulations. *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **15**, 11531–
454 11542 (2013). URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1039/C3CP51440D>.
- 455 [8] Schnorr, K. *et al.* Direct tracking of ultrafast proton transfer in water dimers. *Science Advances*
456 **9**, eadg7864 (2023). URL <https://www.science.org/doi/abs/10.1126/sciadv.adg7864>.
- 457 [9] Tachikawa, H. Ionization dynamics of the small-sized water clusters: a direct ab ini-
458 tio trajectory study. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry A* **108**, 7853–7862 (2004). URL
459 <https://doi.org/10.1021/jp0492691>.
- 460 [10] Furuhashi, A., Dupuis, M. & Hirao, K. Reactions associated with ionization in water: A
461 direct ab initio dynamics study of ionization in (H₂O)₁₇. *The Journal of Chemical Physics*
462 **124**, 164310 (2006). URL <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.2194904>.
- 463 [11] Marsalek, O. *et al.* Chasing charge localization and chemical reactivity following pho-
464 toionization in liquid water. *The Journal of Chemical Physics* **135** (2011). URL <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.3664746>.
- 465
- 466 [12] Loh, Z.-H. *et al.* Observation of the fastest chemical processes in the radiolysis of water.
467 *Science* **367**, 179–182 (2020). URL [https://www.science.org/doi/abs/10.1126/science.](https://www.science.org/doi/abs/10.1126/science.aaz4740)
468 [aaz4740](https://www.science.org/doi/abs/10.1126/science.aaz4740).
- 469 [13] Lin, M.-F. *et al.* Imaging the short-lived hydroxyl-hydronium pair in ionized liquid water.
470 *Science* **374**, 92–95 (2021). URL [https://www.science.org/doi/abs/10.1126/science.](https://www.science.org/doi/abs/10.1126/science.abg3091)
471 [abg3091](https://www.science.org/doi/abs/10.1126/science.abg3091).
- 472 [14] Richter, C. *et al.* Competition between proton transfer and intermolecular coulombic de-
473 cay in water. *Nature Communications* **9**, 4988 (2018). URL [https://doi.org/10.1038/](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-018-07501-6)
474 [s41467-018-07501-6](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-018-07501-6).
- 475 [15] Thürmer, S. *et al.* On the nature and origin of dicationic, charge-separated species formed
476 in liquid water on x-ray irradiation. *Nature Chemistry* **5**, 590–596 (2013). URL [https://doi.org/10.1038/](https://doi.org/10.1038/nchem.1680)
477 [nchem.1680](https://doi.org/10.1038/nchem.1680).
- 478 [16] Bernhard, W. A. *Radical Reaction Pathways Initiated by Direct Energy Deposition in DNA by*
479 *Ionizing Radiation*, chap. 2, 41–68 (John Wiley & Sons, Ltd). URL <https://onlinelibrary>.

- 480 [wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/9780470526279.ch2](https://doi.org/10.1002/9780470526279.ch2).
- 481 [17] Florián, J. & Leszczyński, J. Spontaneous dna mutations induced by proton transfer in the
482 guanine-cytosine base pairs: An energetic perspective. *Journal of the American Chemical*
483 *Society* **118**, 3010–3017 (1996). URL <https://doi.org/10.1021/ja951983g>.
- 484 [18] Kumar, A. & Sevilla, M. D. Proton-coupled electron transfer in dna on formation of radiation-
485 produced ion radicals. *Chemical Reviews* **110**, 7002–7023 (2010). URL [https://doi.org/](https://doi.org/10.1021/cr100023g)
486 [10.1021/cr100023g](https://doi.org/10.1021/cr100023g).
- 487 [19] Srivastava, R. The role of proton transfer on mutations. *Frontiers in Chemistry* **7** (2019).
488 URL <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fchem.2019.00536>.
- 489 [20] Golan, A. *et al.* Ionization of dimethyluracil dimers leads to facile proton transfer in the
490 absence of hydrogen bonds. *Nature Chemistry* **4**, 323–329 (2012). URL [https://doi.org/](https://doi.org/10.1038/nchem.1298)
491 [10.1038/nchem.1298](https://doi.org/10.1038/nchem.1298).
- 492 [21] Yin, Z. *et al.* Femtosecond proton transfer in urea solutions probed by x-ray spectroscopy.
493 *Nature* **619**, 749–754 (2023). URL <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-023-06182-6>.
- 494 [22] Agmon, N. The grotthuss mechanism. *Chemical Physics Letters* **244**, 456–462 (1995). URL
495 <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/000926149500905J>.
- 496 [23] Khistyayev, K. *et al.* Proton transfer in nucleobases is mediated by water. *The Journal of*
497 *Physical Chemistry A* **117**, 6789–6797 (2013). URL <https://doi.org/10.1021/jp406029p>.
- 498 [24] Johnny, M. *et al.* Water is a radiation protection agent for ionised pyrrole. *Phys. Chem. Chem.*
499 *Phys.* **26**, 13118–13130 (2024). URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1039/D3CP03471B>.
- 500 [25] Alizadeh, E., Orlando, T. M. & Sanche, L. Biomolecular damage induced by ioniz-
501 ing radiation: The direct and indirect effects of low-energy electrons on dna. *Annual*
502 *Review of Physical Chemistry* **66**, 379–398 (2015). URL [https://doi.org/10.1146/](https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-physchem-040513-103605)
503 [annurev-physchem-040513-103605](https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-physchem-040513-103605).
- 504 [26] Pimblott, S. M. & LaVerne, J. A. Production of low-energy electrons by ionizing radiation.
505 *Radiation Physics and Chemistry* **76**, 1244–1247 (2007). URL [https://www.sciencedirect.](https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0969806X07000448)
506 [com/science/article/pii/S0969806X07000448](https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0969806X07000448).
- 507 [27] Bhardwaj, V., Gumber, D., Abbot, V., Dhiman, S. & Sharma, P. Pyrrole: a resourceful
508 small molecule in key medicinal hetero-aromatics. *RSC Adv.* **5**, 15233–15266 (2015). URL
509 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1039/C4RA15710A>.

- 510 [28] Chinchilla, R., Nájera, C. & Yus, M. Metalated heterocycles and their applications in synthetic
511 organic chemistry. *Chemical Reviews* **104**, 2667–2722 (2004). URL [https://doi.org/10.](https://doi.org/10.1021/cr020101a)
512 [1021/cr020101a](https://doi.org/10.1021/cr020101a).
- 513 [29] Skitnevskaya, A. D. *et al.* Two-sided impact of water on the relaxation of inner-valence
514 vacancies of biologically relevant molecules. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry Letters* **14**,
515 1418–1426 (2023). URL <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcllett.2c03654>.
- 516 [30] van den Brom, A. J. *et al.* Photodissociation and photoionization of pyrrole following the
517 multiphoton excitation at 243 and 364.7 nm. *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **7**, 892–899 (2005).
518 URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.1039/B415766D>.
- 519 [31] Ullrich, J. *et al.* Recoil-ion and electron momentum spectroscopy: reaction-microscopes.
520 *Reports on Progress in Physics* **66**, 1463 (2003). URL [https://dx.doi.org/10.1088/](https://dx.doi.org/10.1088/0034-4885/66/9/203)
521 [0034-4885/66/9/203](https://dx.doi.org/10.1088/0034-4885/66/9/203).
- 522 [32] Dörner, R. *et al.* Cold Target Recoil Ion Momentum Spectroscopy: a ‘momentum microscope’
523 to view atomic collision dynamics. *Physics Reports* **330**, 95–192 (2000). URL [https://www.](https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S037015739900109X)
524 [sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S037015739900109X](https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S037015739900109X).
- 525 [33] Zobeley, J., Santra, R. & Cederbaum, L. S. Electronic decay in weakly bound heteroclusters:
526 Energy transfer versus electron transfer. *The Journal of Chemical Physics* **115**, 5076–5088
527 (2001). URL <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.1395555>.
- 528 [34] Förstel, M., Mucke, M., Arion, T., Bradshaw, A. M. & Hergenhahn, U. Autoionization
529 mediated by electron transfer. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **106**, 033402 (2011). URL [https://link.](https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevLett.106.033402)
530 [aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevLett.106.033402](https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevLett.106.033402).
- 531 [35] Sakai, K. *et al.* Electron-transfer-mediated decay and interatomic coulombic decay from the
532 triply ionized states in argon dimers. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **106**, 033401 (2011). URL [https:](https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevLett.106.033401)
533 [//link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevLett.106.033401](https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevLett.106.033401).
- 534 [36] Cederbaum, L. S., Zobeley, J. & Tarantelli, F. Giant intermolecular decay and fragmentation
535 of clusters. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **79**, 4778–4781 (1997). URL [https://link.aps.org/doi/10.](https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevLett.79.4778)
536 [1103/PhysRevLett.79.4778](https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevLett.79.4778).
- 537 [37] Wang, Z. *et al.* Directly imaging excited state-resolved transient structures of water induced
538 by valence and inner-shell ionisation. *Nature Communications* **14**, 5420 (2023). URL [https:](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-41204-x)
539 [//doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-41204-x](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-41204-x).

- 540 [38] Sarkar, S., Ramanathan, N. & Sundararajan, K. Effect of methyl substitution on the N–H...O
541 interaction in complexes of pyrrole with water, methanol, and dimethyl ether: Matrix isolation
542 infrared spectroscopy and ab initio computational studies. *The Journal of Physical Chemistry*
543 *A* **122**, 2445–2460 (2018). URL <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpca.8b00023>.
- 544 [39] Vendrell, O., Stoychev, S. D. & Cederbaum, L. S. Generation of highly damaging
545 H₂O⁺ radicals by inner valence shell ionization of water. *ChemPhysChem* **11**, 1006–1009
546 (2010). URL [https://chemistry-europe.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/](https://chemistry-europe.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/cphc.201000034)
547 [cphc.201000034](https://chemistry-europe.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/cphc.201000034).
- 548 [40] Zhou, J. *et al.* Real-time observation of ultrafast molecular rotation in weakly bound
549 dimers. *Phys. Rev. Res.* **3**, 023050 (2021). URL [https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/](https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevResearch.3.023050)
550 [PhysRevResearch.3.023050](https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevResearch.3.023050).
- 551 [41] Zhou, J. *et al.* Ultrafast charge and proton transfer in doubly ionized ammonia dimers. *The*
552 *Journal of Physical Chemistry Letters* **13**, 10603–10611 (2022). URL [https://doi.org/10.](https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcllett.2c02560)
553 [1021/acs.jpcllett.2c02560](https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcllett.2c02560).
- 554 [42] Dereka, B. *et al.* Crossover from hydrogen to chemical bonding. *Science* **371**, 160–164 (2021).
555 URL <https://www.science.org/doi/abs/10.1126/science.abe1951>.
- 556 [43] Hans, A. *et al.* Suppression of x-ray-induced radiation damage to biomolecules in aqueous
557 environments by immediate intermolecular decay of inner-shell vacancies. *The Journal of*
558 *Physical Chemistry Letters* **12**, 7146–7150 (2021). URL [https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.](https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcllett.1c01879)
559 [jpcllett.1c01879](https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcllett.1c01879).
- 560 [44] Ren, X. *et al.* Experimental evidence for ultrafast intermolecular relaxation processes in
561 hydrated biomolecules. *Nature Physics* **14**, 1062–1066 (2018). URL [https://doi.org/10.](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41567-018-0214-9)
562 [1038/s41567-018-0214-9](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41567-018-0214-9).
- 563 [45] Nomura, S. *et al.* Dissociation of biomolecules in liquid environments during fast heavy-ion
564 irradiation. *The Journal of Chemical Physics* **147**, 225103 (2017). URL [https://doi.org/](https://doi.org/10.1063/1.5009367)
565 [10.1063/1.5009367](https://doi.org/10.1063/1.5009367).
- 566 [46] Neustetter, M., Mahmoodi-Darian, M. & Denifl, S. Study of electron ionization and frag-
567 mentation of non-hydrated and hydrated tetrahydrofuran clusters. *Journal of the Ameri-*
568 *can Society for Mass Spectrometry* **28**, 866–872 (2017). URL [https://doi.org/10.1007/](https://doi.org/10.1007/s13361-017-1634-y)
569 [s13361-017-1634-y](https://doi.org/10.1007/s13361-017-1634-y).

- 570 [47] Markush, P. *et al.* The role of the environment in the ion induced fragmentation of uracil.
571 *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **18**, 16721–16729 (2016). URL [http://dx.doi.org/10.1039/](http://dx.doi.org/10.1039/C6CP01940D)
572 [C6CP01940D](http://dx.doi.org/10.1039/C6CP01940D).
- 573 [48] Jahnke, T. *et al.* Interatomic and intermolecular coulombic decay. *Chemical Reviews* **120**,
574 11295–11369 (2020). URL <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemrev.0c00106>.
- 575 [49] Ren, X. *et al.* Ultrafast energy transfer between π -stacked aromatic rings upon inner-
576 valence ionization. *Nature Chemistry* **14**, 232–238 (2022). URL [https://doi.org/10.1038/](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41557-021-00838-4)
577 [s41557-021-00838-4](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41557-021-00838-4).
- 578 [50] Jia, S. *et al.* Cold-target electron-ion-coincidence momentum-spectroscopy study of electron-
579 impact single and double ionization of N_2 and O_2 molecules. *Phys. Rev. A* **107**, 032819 (2023).
580 URL <https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevA.107.032819>.
- 581 [51] Frisch, M. J. *et al.* Gaussian 16 Revision A.03 (2016). Gaussian Inc. Wallingford CT.
- 582 [52] Schlegel, H. B. *et al.* Ab initio molecular dynamics: Propagating the density matrix with
583 gaussian orbitals. *The Journal of Chemical Physics* **114**, 9758–9763 (2001). URL <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.1372182>.
- 584 [53] Iyengar, S. S. *et al.* Ab initio molecular dynamics: Propagating the density matrix with gaus-
585 sian orbitals. ii. generalizations based on mass-weighting, idempotency, energy conservation
586 and choice of initial conditions. *The Journal of Chemical Physics* **115**, 10291–10302 (2001).
587 URL <https://aip.scitation.org/doi/abs/10.1063/1.1416876>.
- 588 [54] Schlegel, H. B. *et al.* Ab initio molecular dynamics: Propagating the density matrix with
589 gaussian orbitals. iii. comparison with born–oppenheimer dynamics. *The Journal of Chemical*
590 *Physics* **117**, 8694–8704 (2002). URL <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.1514582>.
- 591 [55] Tully, J. C. Molecular dynamics with electronic transitions. *J. Chem. Phys.* **93**, 1061–1071
592 (1990). URL <http://aip.scitation.org/doi/10.1063/1.459170>.
- 593 [56] Slavíček, P., Hollas, D., Svoboda, O. & Ončák, M. ABIN, version 1.1.
594 <https://github.com/PHOTOX/ABIN> (2015). Accessed: 2021-10-11.
- 595 [57] Shiozaki, T. BAGEL: Brilliantly Advanced General Electronic-structure Library. *WIREs*
596 *Comput. Mol. Sci.* **8**, e1331 (2018). URL <https://doi.org/10.1002/wcms.1331>.
- 597 [58] Ceriotti, M., Bussi, G. & Parrinello, M. Nuclear quantum effects in solids using a colored-
598 noise thermostat. *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **103**, 030603 (2009). URL [https://link.aps.org/doi/](https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevLett.103.030603)
599 [10.1103/PhysRevLett.103.030603](https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevLett.103.030603).
- 600

- 601 [59] Ceriotti, M., Bussi, G. & Parrinello, M. Colored-noise thermostats à la Carte. *J. Chem. Theory*
602 *Comput.* **6**, 1170–1180 (2010). URL <https://pubs.acs.org/sharingguidelines>.
- 603 [60] Ceriotti, M., Manolopoulos, D. E. & Parrinello, M. Accelerating the convergence of path
604 integral dynamics with a generalized Langevin equation. *J. Chem. Phys.* **134**, 9 (2011). URL
605 <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.3556661>.
- 606 [61] Titov, A. V., Ufimtsev, I. S., Luehr, N. & Martinez, T. J. Generating Efficient Quantum
607 Chemistry Codes for Novel Architectures. *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* **9**, 213–221 (2013). URL
608 <https://doi.org/10.1021/ct300321a>.
- 609 [62] Epifanovsky, E. *et al.* Software for the frontiers of quantum chemistry: An overview of
610 developments in the q-chem 5 package. *J. Chem. Phys.* **155**, 084801 (2021). URL <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0055522>.
611 <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0055522>.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

621 X.R., P.S. and C.W. conceived and supervised the project. J.Z., S.J., X.X., X.H., Q.Z.,
622 Q.M., Y.Z., and X.R. performed the electron-impact experiments and analyzed the data.
623 L.W., X.L., L.H., S.L., D.Z., C.W., and D.D. performed the laser experiments. J.Z, Q.M.,
624 and X.R. carried out the Born-Oppenheimer molecular dynamics simulations. M.B. and
625 P.S. performed the nonadiabatic molecular dynamics simulations. A.D.S., M.B., A.D.T.,
626 and P.S. calculated the potential energy surfaces. J.Z., M.B., C.W., P.S., and X.R. wrote

627 the first draft of the manuscript. All authors contributed to the interpretation of the data
628 and commented on the manuscript.

COMPETING INTERESTS

629 The authors declare no competing interests.